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Research Article

**PLEIOTROPIC EFFECTS OF METFORMIN: FROM
CELLULAR TARGETS TO SYSTEMIC OUTCOMES****Chillimunta Bhavani, Saroyar Reja, Mehedi Hasan, Subiya Maheen, Panala Teja Sri
Mahalaxmi, Md Ashik Malithya, Narender Boggula***

Omega College of Pharmacy, Edulabad, Ghatkesar, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

Abstract:

Metformin is the first-choice therapy to lower glycaemia and manage type 2 diabetes. Continuously emerging epidemiological data and experimental models are showing additional protective effects of metformin against a number of age-related diseases (ARDs), e.g., cardiovascular diseases and cancer. Metformin, classified as a biguanide oral antidiabetic agent, is predominantly prescribed as the primary treatment for type 2 diabetes mellitus. Its role as a therapeutic agent is expanding to include the treatment of pre-diabetes, gestational diabetes, polycystic ovarian disease and the treatment or prevention of preeclampsia. Beyond its primary role in regulating blood sugar, it also provides several secondary health advantages. These include protective cardiovascular effects, potential roles in managing COVID-19, assistance with weight control particularly in PCOS, and promising anti-cancer, anti-aging, and neuroprotective properties. This review summarizes recent studies supporting these diverse effects and discusses the methodologies of significant research efforts. Particular focus is given to metformin's mechanisms of action, key clinical trials, and observational studies that demonstrate its extended therapeutic utility.

Key words: Metformin, COVID-19, polycystic ovarian syndrome, anti-aging, neurodegenerative disorders, *Galega officinalis*.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Narender Boggula**

Associate Professor,

Omega College of Pharmacy,

Edulabad, Ghatkesar, Hyderabad, Telangana, India - 501 301.

E-Mail: drnarenderboggula@gmail.com

Mobile: +91 96 66 55 2211

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Historically, *Galega officinalis*, known by names such as goat's rue or French lilac, was used in medieval Europe as a folk remedy to alleviate symptoms now recognized as indicators of diabetes mellitus, such as frequent urination. In 1914, this plant was found to contain guanidine and related compounds, making up 0.10–0.7% of its dry content. Although guanidine was observed to lower blood glucose in rabbits in 1918, its toxicity made it unsuitable for clinical use. By 1929, researchers synthesized various biguanides, including metformin, which retained guanidine's anti-diabetic effects but with reduced toxicity.

Following decades of clinical use in countries like Canada and across Europe, the FDA approved metformin for treating type 2 diabetes in the United States in 1995. In 2012, major diabetes organizations recommended metformin as the first-line treatment for type 2 diabetes. Due to its effectiveness, affordability, and safety, metformin is now the most widely prescribed oral antidiabetic medication, used by over 150 million individuals each year.

Over the years, metformin's utility has expanded beyond blood glucose control. It has demonstrated potential benefits in treating various conditions such as cancers (including breast, colorectal, and endometrial), obesity, liver and kidney disorders, and

cardiovascular diseases. Moreover, its anti-inflammatory and metabolic regulatory properties have prompted researchers to explore its potential in managing COVID-19, slowing aging, and offering neuroprotection. Clinical and preclinical data support its multifaceted benefits, attributed largely to its metabolic actions, improved insulin sensitivity, reduction in oxidative stress, and protection of vascular and mitochondrial function [1-3]. This review aims to explore these secondary therapeutic effects and shed light on the mechanisms that may be responsible.

Metformin and diabetes

Metformin (1,1-dimethyl biguanide) is a low-molecular-weight compound derived from guanidine, which exists in the human body as a cationic molecule (Figure 1). It was synthesized based on the chemical structure of guanidine derivatives extracted from the European medicinal plant *Galega officinalis* L. (Fabaceae), which has been used for curative purposes since the Middle Ages. Various documents attest that as early as the XVIII century, herbal preparations containing the aerial flowering parts of galega were recommended for people affected by persistent thirst and frequent urine emissions, characteristic symptoms of diabetes mellitus (DM). Subsequently, guanidine and its natural derivative, galegine, were investigated as antidiabetic drugs, demonstrating not only hypoglycemic effects but also some toxicity.

Figure 1: The natural compounds guanidine and galegine recognized in *Galega officinalis* and the synthetic derivative metformin that is mainly used in the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus

Figure 2: Actions of Metformin. LDH- Lactate dehydrogenase; DHAP- Dihydroxyacetone phosphate; NADH- Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide hydrogen; NAD+-Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide; GPD2- Glycerol 3 phosphate dehydrogenase 2; GPD1- Glycerol 3 phosphate dehydrogenase 1; G3P- Glycerol 3 phosphate

Extensive research and clinical trials have validated the effectiveness of metformin, either alone or in combination with other glucose-lowering agents, in managing type 2 diabetes (T2D). In a 2006 clinical trial comparing metformin, glibenclamide, and rosiglitazone, metformin showed a moderate decrease in fasting glucose levels, outperforming rosiglitazone but not glibenclamide. Combinations of metformin with other antidiabetic drugs often yield better glycemic control. For instance, metformin combined with glibenclamide or glimepiride demonstrated superior outcomes compared to metformin alone. Pairing metformin with troglitazone also led to greater reductions in both fasting and postprandial glucose levels. Furthermore, combinations with newer agents like DPP-4 inhibitors, SGLT2 inhibitors, and GLP-1 receptor agonists have proven effective without increasing the risk of hypoglycemia.

When used alongside insulin, metformin improves glycemic control and reduces weight gain more effectively than monotherapy. In addition, studies in patients with cognitive impairments and abnormal glucose metabolism showed improvements in insulin sensitivity and fasting insulin levels with metformin use. Metformin is also used in pregnancy, particularly for T2D, gestational diabetes (GDM), and polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), where it showed better weight reduction compared to rosiglitazone. Despite

its growing acceptance in pregnancy, safety concerns persist, as some studies indicate a higher risk of obesity and metabolic issues in offspring exposed to metformin.

Long-term use may also increase the risk of beta-cell failure and insulin resistance, underscoring the need for extended follow-up studies. Mechanistically, metformin lowers blood glucose primarily by inhibiting hepatic glucose production via both AMPK-dependent and independent pathways. Through AMPK activation, metformin suppresses gluconeogenic genes (like G6Pase, PEPCK, and PC) and inhibits mTORC1, leading to decreased glucose production. Independently, it interferes with glucagon signaling and inhibits mitochondrial GPD, impairing lactate's conversion into glucose. Metformin also directly targets FBP1, a key enzyme in gluconeogenesis.

Beyond the liver, metformin enhances glucose uptake in muscles via GLUT4 and promotes intestinal glucose absorption reduction. It increases GLP-1 secretion, thereby boosting insulin release. Recently, the gut microbiota has been identified as another target of metformin. Alterations in microbial composition, such as reduced *Bacteroides fragilis* and increased GUDCA, contribute to improved glucose tolerance by modulating FXR signaling in the gut [2-4].

Metformin and Covid-19

While vaccines have proven effective against severe COVID-19 caused by SARS-CoV-2 variants, early outpatient treatment remains crucial, especially in light of unequal global vaccine access, variable uptake, and the risk of emerging variants. Metformin, through its potential geroscience-based benefits, may enhance immune resilience in older adults when infected with both current and future pathogens.

At the start of the pandemic, several existing drugs were considered for COVID-19 treatment, though many lacked scientific justification and failed to show efficacy. However, a growing body of evidence indicates that metformin may be beneficial in this context. Meta-analyses of observational studies have reported that metformin use is linked to reduced hospitalization and mortality among COVID-19 patients. Two retrospective analyses using the National COVID Cohort Collaborative (N3C) database found that metformin helped reduce the risk of severe COVID-19 in individuals with prediabetes and was associated with lower rates of mechanical ventilation and mortality-especially in women-when compared with sulfonyleureas.

Metformin has also shown benefits in hospitalized COVID-19 patients. In one study involving diabetic patients, those taking metformin had reduced inflammation, shorter hospital stays, and lower intubation rates. Its mechanisms of action in this setting involve activation of AMPK through liver kinase B1, SIRT1 activation, stimulation of PGC-1 α , and inhibition of mitochondrial complex 1, NF- κ B, and mTORC1. Additionally, metformin has demonstrated *in vitro* activity against several RNA viruses including Zika, dengue, hepatitis B and C, influenza, and HIV-some of which it has shown efficacy against since the 1940s.

Its immune-modulating and anti-inflammatory effects are particularly relevant for COVID-19. Metformin reduces levels of cytokines like TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6, CXCL5, CXCL10, and MCP-1. It also inhibits STAT3 and suppresses neutrophil extracellular traps. Moreover, metformin may prevent NLRP3 inflammasome activation. Pre-COVID users of metformin have shown lower levels of inflammatory markers like CRP and ferritin in ICU settings.

Metformin's inhibition of mTOR, modulation of ACE2 via AMPK-mediated phosphorylation, and suppression of oxidative stress and viral replication pathways further contribute to its therapeutic potential. It may also help prevent pulmonary fibrosis, mast cell

activation, endothelial damage, and thrombosis, while improving cell survival by reducing apoptosis and other forms of cell death. By targeting aging-related mechanisms, metformin could enhance general resilience to infectious diseases. Given its safety, affordability, and accessibility, ongoing clinical trials evaluating metformin for COVID-19 treatment are of high importance [5-8].

Metformin in PCOS

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a prevalent hormonal disorder and the leading cause of infertility in women of reproductive age. It affects up to one in eight women globally, with as many as 70% of cases remaining undiagnosed. Certain ethnic groups anovulatory are disproportionately affected. PCOS is responsible for over 90% of anovulatory infertility cases and is frequently associated with elevated cardiometabolic risks, including impaired glucose regulation, abnormal lipid levels, and sleep apnea. Long-term complications include prediabetes, type 2 diabetes, gestational diabetes, and cardiovascular disease. Additionally, PCOS increases the likelihood of developing metabolic-associated fatty liver disease, which is linked to further serious health risks like liver failure and heart disease.

Women with PCOS often experience challenging symptoms such as obesity, irregular menstruation, and signs of hyperandrogenism-like hair loss, acne, oily skin, and excessive body hair-contributing to poor body image and emotional distress. A key factor in the development of PCOS is insulin resistance and the resulting hyperinsulinemia, which promote excess androgen production by reducing liver synthesis of sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG). Insulin resistance also disrupts hormonal balance within the brain-ovary-adrenal system, increasing the release of hormones such as GnRH, LH, and ACTH. This hormonal imbalance further impairs fertility. Elevated androgen levels also interfere with insulin's ability to recruit GLUT4 transporters, worsening insulin resistance.

Metformin, which has been used in Europe to treat type 2 diabetes for over 60 years, is known for improving insulin sensitivity. While it is primarily indicated for diabetes, it is widely used off-label to manage PCOS and is recommended in several clinical guidelines. The extended-release (XR or SR) formulation, which is better tolerated than the immediate-release form, is typically prescribed at a maximum of 2000 mg per day. Metformin's benefits in PCOS go beyond improving insulin resistance. It also helps reduce the risk of cardiovascular and kidney complications. Although gastrointestinal side effects

are common, they often subside with continued use [9-11].

Metformin in cancer

A growing body of research shows that metformin can inhibit the growth, survival, and spread of various cancer cell types, including those from the breast, liver, bone, pancreas, endometrium, colon, kidney, and lungs. These anti-cancer properties are attributed to both direct and indirect effects on cellular metabolism.

Metformin's direct action involves AMPK-dependent and AMPK-independent mechanisms. First, through AMPK activation, metformin suppresses the mTOR signaling pathway, leading to reduced protein synthesis and, consequently, limited cancer cell growth and division. It also interferes with the interaction between G protein-coupled receptors and insulin signaling, which may hinder pancreatic cancer progression. Additionally, it promotes phosphorylation of p53, a key tumor suppressor, thereby preventing cancer cell invasion and metastasis. Apart from AMPK activation, metformin can independently inhibit mTORC1, an essential regulator of cell growth, and disrupt mitochondrial complex I activity. This inhibition reduces the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), thereby decreasing DNA damage and the risk of cancer development. It also promotes autophagy and programmed cell death (apoptosis) through pathways not reliant on AMPK.

Indirectly, metformin impacts the tumor microenvironment by influencing processes like angiogenesis, fibroblast activity, immune suppression, and macrophage behaviour. By lowering blood glucose levels, it also limits the energy supply available for cancer cells, thus reducing their proliferation and survival. Other mechanisms include modulation of the immune system and suppression of pro-inflammatory cytokines by downregulating NF- κ B activity. Metformin may also alter the expression of microRNAs by enhancing the activity of DICER, a key enzyme in microRNA biogenesis, thus contributing to its anti-tumor effects.

A recent study showed that combining metformin with intermittent fasting (IF) can strongly suppress tumor growth. This effect is achieved by impairing the metabolic flexibility of cancer cells via the PP2A/GSK3 β /MCL-1 axis. As tumors adapt their energy metabolism between glycolysis and oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS), this dual approach disrupts their ability to survive. Importantly, this combination reduced tumor growth without causing

weight loss or toxicity, highlighting promising avenues for future cancer therapies involving metformin [12-14].

Breast cancer

Breast cancer is one of the most frequently diagnosed cancers in women and becomes increasingly common with age. Its progression is driven by several cellular pathways, many of which are closely tied to glucose metabolism. Research indicates that metformin may reduce the risk of developing breast cancer in patients with T2D. Cancer cells are known to consume large amounts of glucose and favour glycolysis over oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS), a phenomenon known as the "Warburg effect." Metformin's ability to lower blood glucose levels limits this energy supply, thereby hindering cancer cell growth. Additionally, it has been shown to reduce the expression of fatty acid synthase (FAS), a key enzyme in the fatty acid synthesis pathway, further compromising cancer cell survival.

Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC), a particularly aggressive and hard-to-treat subtype, lacks effective targeted therapies. A transcription factor called BACH1 (BTB and CNC homology 1) regulates glycolysis and OXPHOS in TNBC and plays a role in the Warburg effect. Previous studies have revealed that heme can suppress BACH1 expression and may be useful in treating TNBC. Recent research demonstrated that a combination therapy using heme and metformin significantly inhibited TNBC tumor growth. These findings offer new perspectives on using metformin in conjunction with other treatments to more effectively combat breast cancer [15-17].

Blood cancer

In blood cancers like multiple myeloma (MM) and leukemia, the AKT signaling pathway plays a central role in disease progression. In MM, high AKT activity is observed even in advanced stages. Studies have shown that metformin inhibits the AKT/mTOR pathway, which suppresses the growth and proliferation of myeloma cells.

Additionally, metformin reduces the expression of glucose regulatory protein 78 (GRP78), a molecule involved in autophagy. This interference enhances apoptosis and strengthens the anti-cancer effects of the proteasome inhibitor bortezomib. Leukemia accounts for 2.8% of all cancers and 3.4% of cancer-related deaths globally. One of its characteristic features is the abnormal activation of the PI3K/AKT/mTOR pathway. Metformin's ability to block this signaling

cascade makes it a potential therapeutic option for treating leukemia.

Furthermore, in cases of lymphoma, metformin has demonstrated anti-tumor effects by inhibiting mTOR activity without involving AKT. This suppression of mTOR activity ultimately limits the growth of both B cells and T cells, which are key components in lymphoma development [18,19].

Colorectal cancer

Colorectal cancer (CRC) ranks among the most prevalent cancers worldwide, with a rising incidence in low- and middle-income countries. Recent studies—including basic research, clinical trials, and population-based analyses—suggest that metformin may serve as a preventive and therapeutic agent against CRC.

The potential mechanisms by which metformin impacts CRC are thought to involve the gut-brain-liver axis, although further investigation is needed. In the intestines, metformin enhances glucose uptake and raises lactate levels. It also increases the concentration of bile acids in the gut, which can influence GLP-1 secretion and cholesterol metabolism. Additionally, metformin modifies the gut microbiota, which plays a crucial role in regulating glucose balance, lipid metabolism, and overall energy homeostasis. These metabolic changes contribute to the suppression of CRC development and progression, highlighting metformin's promise as a chemopreventive strategy [20,21].

Endometrial cancer

Endometrial cancer is the fifth most common malignancy in women, with its incidence rising globally in both developed and developing nations. It is often associated with metabolic disturbances such as obesity and high blood sugar—hallmarks of metabolic syndrome—which contribute to its development. Metformin, known for its anti-diabetic effects, has shown promising results in improving outcomes for patients with endometrial cancer, particularly those with diabetes. Clinical studies have reported improved survival rates among diabetic patients receiving metformin.

The anti-cancer effects of metformin in endometrial cancer are mainly driven by its suppression of mitochondrial oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS) and activation of AMPK. These actions result in the inhibition of multiple metabolic and signaling pathways, including STAT3, ZEB-1, ACC, mTOR, and IGF-1. As a result, protein synthesis and fatty acid

production are reduced, while cell death through apoptosis and autophagy is promoted. Cell proliferation and progression through the cell cycle are also suppressed, collectively contributing to the inhibition of tumor growth [22,23].

Melanoma

Melanoma is the most aggressive form of skin cancer, responsible for nearly 80% of deaths related to skin malignancies. Its invasive nature often leads to metastasis in the lymph nodes, liver, lungs, and even the central nervous system. Despite the availability of immunotherapies like ipilimumab (anti-CTLA-4) and nivolumab (anti-PD-1), around 55–60% of patients do not respond, highlighting the urgent need for new treatments.

Studies have shown that metformin can induce cell cycle arrest at the G₀–G₁ phase in melanoma cells, thereby inhibiting their proliferation. Additionally, research indicates that metformin can reduce melanoma growth and spread by suppressing the expression of tribbles pseudokinase 3 (TRB3), in both diabetic and non-diabetic mouse models. By activating AMPK, metformin can influence melanoma cell survival, proliferation, and the tumor microenvironment. Investigating combination therapies involving metformin and existing treatments could provide promising strategies to enhance melanoma management in the future [24,25].

Bone cancer

In bone cancers, metastatic spread—particularly from breast, lung, and prostate cancers—is more common than cancers originating in bone tissue itself. All types of bone cancers disrupt the normal bone remodeling process, either promoting bone breakdown (osteolysis) or abnormal bone formation (osteoblastic activity), depending on how they affect osteoclast and osteoblast activity.

One of the key regulators of osteoclast development is RANKL (receptor activator of nuclear factor kappa-B ligand), and its activity can be inhibited through AMPK activation by metformin. This inhibition reduces osteoclast proliferation and differentiation. Furthermore, metformin has been shown to suppress the proliferation, migration, and invasion of bone cancer cells by interfering with signaling pathways such as AMPK/mTOR/S6 and MMP2/MMP9. These findings suggest that metformin has therapeutic potential not only in primary bone cancers but also in bone metastases [19,26].

Metformin and liver diseases

The liver plays a central role in maintaining glucose and lipid metabolism, making it a primary target for metformin's actions. Liver dysfunction can lead to several conditions, including diabetes, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), cirrhosis, non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC).

Research has shown that metformin is safe for patients with cirrhosis and can lower the risk of death by 57%. Among diabetic patients, metformin use has been associated with a 50% reduction in the incidence of HCC, mainly through its influence on cell growth and angiogenesis via the PI3K/AKT/mTOR pathway.

The effectiveness of metformin in treating NAFLD and hepatitis, however, remains debated. Animal studies have found that metformin prevents fatty liver disease by reducing liver triglyceride levels. In humans, it has been observed to decrease the incidence of fatty liver and induce some histological improvements. However, some studies reported no significant effect of metformin on liver histology or inflammation. Cases of metformin-induced liver toxicity are extremely rare and usually linked to the use of other hepatotoxic drugs.

Metformin's impact on NAFLD is largely through regulation of hepatic lipid metabolism. It inhibits key transcription factors involved in lipogenesis, such as SREBP, ChREBP, and LXR, and reduces the expression of enzymes like FAS and SCD1. Through AMPK activation, it suppresses de novo lipogenesis by reducing ACC and SREBP1c activity. Metformin also enhances fatty acid oxidation, lowers inflammatory cytokines like TNF- α and IL-6, and modulates adipokine synthesis. In the context of HCC, the mTOR pathway appears to play a pivotal role. Furthermore, metformin has been shown to induce FGF21 expression, offering additional protection against diet-induced fatty liver disease [26,27].

Metformin and cardiovascular diseases

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) remains one of the leading causes of death and disability worldwide. Several factors contribute to CVD risk, including smoking, diabetes, obesity, high cholesterol, and hypertension. Both type 1 and type 2 diabetes are often found alongside cardiovascular complications. Hyperglycemia contributes to CVD by promoting oxidative stress, which impairs lipoprotein and endothelial function, raising the risk of vascular damage.

Metformin, a well-established anti-hyperglycemic drug, has been shown to reduce the incidence of CVD among diabetic patients. By activating AMPK, metformin prevents harmful modifications to high-density lipoprotein (HDL) particles and reduces low-density lipoprotein (LDL) modifications. These improvements enhance cholesterol transport and lower cardiovascular risk. In addition, metformin alleviates oxidative stress in endothelial cells and reduces hyperglycemia-induced inflammation, both of which are critical contributors to CVD development. Type 2 diabetes also significantly increases the risk of heart failure, accounting for roughly one-third of cases.

Metformin improves myocardial energy metabolism by optimizing glucose and lipid handling in cardiac cells through AMPK activation. A recent randomized controlled trial in patients with coronary artery disease but without diabetes demonstrated that metformin significantly reduces left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH)-a strong predictor of adverse cardiac outcomes. Treatment also led to reductions in left ventricular mass, body weight, and oxidative stress markers. Given its multiple cardiovascular benefits in both diabetic and non-diabetic populations, metformin presents a promising therapeutic option for broader CVD management in the future [3,27,28].

Metformin and aging

Aging is an ineluctable natural process influenced by both inheritable and environmental factors, frequently leading to a decline in quality of life, increased frailty, and advanced hospitalization rates. Throughout history, humans have sought ways to delay aging and extend healthy lifetime. Crucial natural features of growing include reduced towel rejuvenescence and bloodied homeostasis, which contribute to the development of conditions like diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, cancer, osteoporosis, depression, and neurodegenerative conditions similar as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's.

Aging is primarily driven by DNA damage and dislocations in autophagy. DNA damage results from oxidative stress (caused by ROS), chemical agents, or radiation, while inheritable and environmental influences affecting autophagy also accelerate aging. Although studies in *Caenorhabditis elegans* showed that metformin can extend lifetime, analogous direct anti-aging goods haven't been easily observed in humans. still, clinical data suggest that metformin improves aging-related conditions, similar as diabetes and cardiovascular conditions, which laterally contribute to increased lifetime and better health issues. In diabetic cases, metformin has been

associated with a 42% reduction in the threat of diabetes-related deaths. Another clinical trial set up a 24-week course of metformin that bettered cognitive function and reduced depressive symptoms.

Metformin's impact on aging is largely tied to its effects on metabolism. By inhibiting mitochondrial complex, I, it lowers the production of ROS, thereby reducing DNA damage. It also activates AMPK, which in turn suppresses the NF- κ B pathway, leading to reduced inflammation. also, metformin decreases insulin situations and inhibits IGF- 1 and mTOR signaling, promoting salutary goods on autophagy and inflammation.

Arising substantiation suggests that metformin's modulation of the gut microbiota may also impact aging. likewise, by enhancing neuronal survival and reducing neuronal damage under conditions of oxygen/ glucose privation, metformin offers neuroprotective benefits. Altogether, these findings support metformin's eventuality as a pharmacological agent for managing aging-related conditions in both diabetic and non-diabetic individualities [6,29].

Metformin and renal diseases

Acute kidney injury (AKI) and chronic kidney disease (CKD) are two major forms of renal dysfunction. AKI involves a sudden decline in kidney function over hours or days, while CKD refers to a gradual, long-

term loss of renal function. Effective treatments for these conditions are still limited. Diabetes is a significant risk factor for kidney diseases, making metformin a drug of interest in this area. Although its use in patients with kidney impairment was previously restricted due to safety concerns, more recent studies suggest that metformin, when administered appropriately, can provide renal protection.

Daily oral administration of metformin has been shown to alleviate kidney fibrosis and restore normal kidney structure and function, primarily by activating the AMPK signaling pathway, which regulates cell growth and energy balance. In animal models of CKD, metformin suppressed kidney injury and improved renal performance through AMPK-mediated regulation of ACC signaling. In human studies, continuous metformin use has also demonstrated benefits, not only for patients with diabetes-induced kidney damage but also for those with non-diabetic kidney diseases. Clinical trials have reported improved kidney function and survival rates among AKI and CKD patients treated with metformin.

However, careful attention to dosing is essential to ensure safety and maximize benefits. Metformin's kidney-protective effects appear to involve improvements in glucose metabolism, reductions in cellular inflammation, and decreased oxidative stress within renal tissues [16,30].

Figure 3: Summary of metformin in different diseases and the underlying major mechanisms

Metformin and neurodegenerative disorders

Although neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's disease (AD), Parkinson's disease (PD), Huntington's disease, and multiple sclerosis (MS) present differently, they share several underlying pathological mechanisms. These include oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, neuroinflammation, protein misfolding, and eventual neuronal loss.

In all four conditions, activated microglia and astrocytes release inflammatory mediators that damage neurons and myelin, contributing to disease progression. Protein aggregation—such as amyloid-beta and tau in AD, α -synuclein in PD, and mutant huntingtin in Huntington's disease—is a hallmark of these disorders. Similarly, oxidative stress and mitochondrial failure lead to energy deficits and cellular damage. Axonal transport disruption, synaptic dysfunction, and impaired proteostasis are common features, culminating in the loss of key neuronal populations, such as dopaminergic neurons in PD and hippocampal neurons in AD.

Mechanism of action in neurodegenerative disorders

Metformin has emerged as a promising neuroprotective agent. Originally developed to regulate blood glucose, it has demonstrated beneficial effects on neuronal health beyond its metabolic actions. By influencing fundamental biological processes—such as cellular energy metabolism and inflammation—metformin offers potential therapeutic benefits for neurodegenerative diseases.

Its neuroprotective effects are linked to several mechanisms:

- *Protein homeostasis:* Metformin inhibits protein misfolding and aggregation, reducing toxic aggregates of α -synuclein, amyloid-beta, tau, and huntingtin. It also prevents the prion-like spread of misfolded proteins between neurons and enhances their degradation through autophagy and the proteasome system.
- *Neuroinflammation:* Metformin suppresses microglial activation and decreases the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines like TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6. It promotes anti-inflammatory phenotypes in glial cells and inhibits the NF- κ B signaling pathway.
- *Oxidative stress and mitochondrial protection:* Through AMPK activation and mitochondrial regulation, metformin reduces oxidative damage and improves neuronal survival.
- *Broader neuroprotection:* By improving glucose metabolism in the brain and reducing neuroinflammation, metformin may enhance resilience against the neurodegenerative processes underlying AD, PD, MS, and Huntington's disease.

As the global burden of neurodegenerative diseases continues to rise with an aging population, repurposing well-known drugs like metformin could accelerate the development of new therapeutic strategies [30-33].

Figure 4: The potential of Metformin as a neuroprotective agent is noteworthy. Metformin possesses the capability to counteract protein hyperphosphorylation, oxidative stress, and neuroinflammation—factors recognized as contributors to neurodegeneration. This compound can exert its effects on neurons while also targeting astrocytes and microglia. As a result, Metformin is able to influence the inflammatory status and glucose metabolism throughout the brain, thereby reducing neuroinflammation and functioning as an antioxidant, which ultimately leads to protein dephosphorylation. The Pentose Phosphate Pathway (PPP) is also a relevant aspect in this context.

CONCLUSION:

Metformin has long been the cornerstone of type 2 diabetes management, but its story extends far beyond glycemic control. As revealed in this review, metformin demonstrates a remarkable range of secondary benefits-spanning from cardiovascular protection and cancer suppression to neuroprotection and potential anti-aging effects. Its ability to modulate key molecular pathways, including AMPK, mTOR, and mitochondrial respiration, allows it to impact several physiological systems simultaneously. These pleiotropic effects, supported by growing clinical and preclinical evidence, make metformin an increasingly valuable tool not only in diabetes care but also in addressing some of the most pressing health challenges of our time, including cancer, neurodegeneration, and metabolic syndromes.

While many of its mechanisms are now better understood, ongoing research continues to reveal new therapeutic potentials. As metformin moves from being a strictly antidiabetic agent to a broader metabolic modulator, its safety profile, affordability, and widespread availability make it a promising candidate for drug repurposing. However, to fully realize its potential, well-designed long-term clinical trials are essential to further validate these secondary applications and clarify any limitations. Ultimately, metformin exemplifies how an old drug can offer new hope across diverse areas of medicine.

Author contributions

All authors made a significant contribution to the work reported, took part in drafting, revising or critically reviewing the article; gave final approval of the version to be published; have agreed on the journal to which the article has been submitted; and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Disclosure

All authors report no conflicts of interest in this work.

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